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Analysing novelty in science: The case of argumentation

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Introduction

There is increasing emphasis on novelty in science (Cohen, 2017). Research that is thought to be novel is not only more easily accepted in top tier journals, sometimes it is required to demonstrate novelty of research to receive grants and funding. Science has deeply rooted incentive system that rewards priority (Merton, 1957) which encourages originality of thought and new lines of inquiry. Pressures for novelty influence the trajectories of research programs and the shape of science in general (Foster, Rzhetsky, & Evans, 2015). So, novelty has impact on both policy making and on structure of science, and it is no wonder there is a lot of interest in assessing novelty of research.

Literature suggests there are several ways in which a novelty of paper might be assessed. First approach is based on the established paths of knowledge creation, as scores on cited references. This idea was proposed by Uzzi and colleagues (2013) who say that a paper is creative, and thus novel, if it has many atypical combinations of references. Next, Wang, Veugelers, and Stephan (2017) define novelty using another combinatorial aspect, namely checking whether a paper creates a combination of referenced journals for the first time ever. Other examples of measuring novelty are clustering of scientific words, where clusters represent different scientific areas, and new clusters and new content of clusters represent novelty of scientific areas (Small et al., 2014). More recently, there have been text mining approaches to novelty, as in Yan, Tian, and Zhang (2020) according to whom novelty of a document has two dimensions – new combinations and new components. The authors define new combinations as the combination of knowledge elements (keywords) of a research area in a new way, and new components as newly introduced knowledge elements.

These approaches to assessing novelty are based on quantitative analysis, where it is studied as different statistics of keywords, or as different combinations of sources, or some combination of the two. Although very effective in discovering statistical patterns in large quantities of data, these approaches assume that novelty is a uniform concept, always having the same weight across different areas of knowledge. Practice tells us that there are different forms of novelty that can be manifested as new theoretical concepts, new methods, new dataset, and new phenomenon under analysis (Dirk, 1999; Shibayama et al., 2021). In addition, in some cases we can obtain erroneous measures of novelty, as for example when a synonym of well-established concept is used in a text.

In this work we categorise keywords of articles published in argumentation community based on different types of novelty. We have previously collected documents that have the word argumentation in their title abstract and keywords, published from 2000 to 2019 in English, from Scopus database. We then performed bibliometric analysis of documents using VOSviewer and obtained a map with 9 clusters of most significant terms. Next, we follow the procedure of Yan, Tian, and Zhang (2020) to identify new knowledge elements and new components of knowledge in our dataset, and then we classify the novelty of those terms according to several categories.

We then proceed with analysis of exemplary cases to analyse them in depth to check meanings of terms and verify findings with experts from argumentation community. Our approach thus combines two standard modes of analysis of novelty, bibliometrics and expert analysis, and it contributes to both understanding of different forms of novelty and to identification of novelty in the community of argumentation.

Novelty in science

Novelty and creativity are one of the core goals of scientific endeavours (Wagner et al., 2019). Scientific prestige is based on reputation system of science, that can be reinforced through priority of discovery (Merton, 1973). Publishing original ideas can lead to breakthroughs in science (March, 1991) and to generating more long-term impact of research (Wang et al., 2017). Thus, it is no surprise that novelty is ever more required attribute that article must satisfy to be accepted in top tier journals. Consequently, the novelty of one's work will determine the funding they receive.

There have been various attempts to assess the indicators of novelty in research. According to Lee and colleagues (2015) novelty can be evaluated as an ex-post measure of impact, when experts, peers, or users assess the creativity of scientific output. They also suggest evaluating the drivers of creativity and the consequences they have on impact and novelty. Within this direction of research is the combinatorial approach to novelty, where scientific papers that introduce unusual combinations of references are thought to represent more novel knowledge (Uzzi et al., 2013). Similar, work of Wand et al. (2017) define novelty as combination of references that is made for the first time ever.

Although these approaches are gaining popularity in literature, there are some critiques to them, especially that creative ideas, and consequentially novelty, are not necessarily inspired by past publications but rather by interdisciplinary connections, discussions with colleagues, and practical solutions to problems (Tahamtan & Bornmann, 2018). In addition, sometimes these approaches are often capturing papers interdisciplinarity rather than its novelty (Fontana et al., 2020). For this, and for the constraint of the approaches to only journal articles, we turn to other direction for measuring the novelty that is based on text mining. We follow the procedure introduced by Yan et al. (2020) according to whom novelty of a document has two dimensions – new combinations and new components. The authors define new combinations as the combination of knowledge elements (keywords) of a research area in a new way, and new components as newly introduced knowledge elements.

Case study. Argumentation

To analyse different forms of novelty we present a case study in the community of argumentation studies. A bibliometric analysis showed that our focal field is characterized by multiple and interconnected communities adopting different theoretical and methodological approaches.

Argumentation theory has a long tradition that reaches back to ancient Greek philosophy and rhetoric (Walton, 2009). With the beginning of the new century, the concept of argumentation expanded from classical rhetoric, logic, and dialectic to other areas of research at the crossroads between computer science and philosophy (Reed & Koszowy, 2011). Techniques and results obtained in argumentation theory are used in artificial intelligence, education, law, etc. (Abbas & Sawamura, 2009), thus forming interdisciplinary area of inquiry with a common reference to “argumentation”.

A bibliometric study shows that this scientific community is rich with different theories and approaches, with three macro areas of expertise, namely humanities, computer science and education studies, that can be further broken down into several sub-communities. Further, this analysis shows frequent and diverse interconnections between sub-communities. We expect that that a fragmented and interconnected field is characterized by a significant and continuous presence of opportunities where scientists introduce new problems and approaches.

Materials and Methodology

Materials

We present a mixed methods study in our focal field - argumentation theory.

Our initial dataset is a set of documents collected for bibliometric analysis of the community, it was collected from Scopus and contains 10301 documents, that are published in English from 2000 to 2019. A bibliometric analysis of the field shows that the field is “composed” of nine sub-communities, which we identified based on VOSviewer clustering of terms.

Method

In this study, we are aiming at categorising keywords based on different types of novelty – new keywords and new combinations of keywords.

We divide our dataset in two groups for pragmatical reasons. First group containing documents published in period 2000-2014, will be our reference documents group against which we compare novelty of documents. Second group are documents published between 2015 and 2019. These documents will be searched for new combinations and new components of keywords that did not appear in previous 5 years, i.e., a document published in 2015 will be compared against documents published in period 2010-2014, documents published in 2016 against ones published between 2011 and 2015, etc. We analyse 5 years against 5 reference periods.

To identify the keywords in our dataset we perform a text mining analysis in R software, using text mining packages “tm”, “tidy”, “RWeka”. We create list of possible keyword combinations (pairs) for each document in a year and compare it with list of possible keyword combinations for each document in reference period to see whether it is new. To calculate new combinations, we divide the number of new combinations with number of possible combinations for that document. To calculate new components, we simply check for each keyword of a document whether it appeared in its reference period and divide the number of new keywords with total number of keywords of the document.

When it comes to newly introduced keywords, we expect them not to be numerous in five-year period for analysis. We will check them case by case, to see whether they are synonyms for

already established problems. If yes, then no novelty is being introduced. If no, they can mean new area of application of theory or they can introduce new parts of theory, and thus mean the expansion of the field.

In addition, we are interested in checking whether combined keywords belong to the same cluster. If not, these combinations can mean novelty, and we intend on checking semantic structure of meaning, to assess if and how meaning of words changes with new combination, by consulting with an expert from the community.

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